

Supplementary Material

Table S1: Actigraphic features

	Feature name	Description
<i>Activity profile</i>	daily act	mean activity for calendar day
	daily acti points	average actipoints score for active (non-sleep) part of day
	daily SD	SD of activity for calendar day
	M10	total activity during the 10 most active hours of the day
	M10 time	midpoint of the 10 most active hours window
	M10 SD	SD of the 10 most active hours window
	M10 RMSSD	RMSSD of the 10 most active hours window
	M10 SlopeEntr	slope entropy for daily M10 window
	RA	relative amplitude between the M10 and L5 periods
	midn2morn	mean activity between 00:00 and 6:00 local time
	morn2noon	mean activity between 6:00 and 12:00 local time
	noon2even	mean activity between 12:00 and 18:00 local time
	even2midn	mean activity between 18:00 and 24:00 local time
<i>Sleep profile</i>	sleep duration	sleep duration for each day in hours
	sleep midtime	midpoint of sleep
	sleep immobile	part of sleep detected as immobile
	sleep active	part of sleep detected as active
	sleep RMSSD	RMSSD of activity during the main daily sleep period
	daily naps	sum of sleep durations of the day shorter than 5 minutes
	L5	total activity during the 5 least active hours of the day
	L5 time	midpoint of the 5 least active hours window
	before fall	activity in 2 hours before the main daily sleep begins
	after fall	activity in 2 hours after the main daily sleep begins
	before wake	activity in 2 hours before the main daily sleep ends
	after wake	activity in 2 hours after the main daily sleep ends
	fall step	step in average activity in 1 hour before and after sleep onset
	wake step	step in average activity in 1 hour before and after wakeup
	WASO	wake after sleep onset is a sum of minutes during a night that are not detected as sleep

The table lists the names of all 28 actigraphic features with their brief descriptions.
(SD—Standard Deviation, RMSSD—Root Mean Square of Successive Differences)

Fig S1: Flow chart of data preprocessing

Actigraphic data were first filtered to retain only days with at least 80% recorded samples, excluding wear-off periods and missing data. For each of these valid days, a set of 28 actigraphic features was computed. Among the 115 patients included in the analysis, 84 exhibited at least one episode of remission and one of relapse. Using these features paired with corresponding daily clinical status labels, two binary classification subsets were constructed: one for mania/remission and another for depression/remission. Each subset included only those patients who experienced at least one episode of remission and one episode of relapse. The data for each subset were split into train and test sets in a 3:2 ratio, ensuring that the split preserved entire clinical episodes to prevent data leakage. Subsequently, data standardization was performed on a per-patient basis using z-scores, with each patient's mean and standard deviation (SD) computed exclusively from their remission-state data in the train set. These remission-based parameters were then used to standardize both the remission and relapse data for that patient across the train and test sets. Following standardization, a Box-Cox power transformation was applied to further normalize the distribution of the features.

Fig S2: Flow chart of model training and evaluation

A Support Vector Machine (SVM) with a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel was employed, using a 3-fold cross-validation (CV) framework. Within each fold, forward feature selection (FFS) was performed using an inner 5-fold CV loop. Actigraphic aggregates selected in at least 2 out of 3 outer folds were used to retrain the final model on the entire train set. The model was then evaluated on the held-out test set.

Fig S3: Mania subset: Predictive power of weekly actigraphic feature aggregates

Effect sizes (standardized mean difference - SMD) with 95% confidence interval (CI) of the selected actigraphic features for mania subsets in each cross-validation (CV) fold. SMD was computed using the mean difference divided by the pooled standard deviation over each fold subset. Aggregates are sorted by effect size and grouped by aggregation approach: mean (μ), standard deviation (σ), and correlation (ρ).

(M10—total activity during the 10 most active hours of the day, L5—total activity during the 5 least active hours of the day, RMSSD—Root Mean Square of Successive Differences, see Supplementary Table S1)

Fig S4: Depression subset: Predictive power of weekly actigraphic feature aggregates

Effect sizes (standardized mean difference - SMD) with 95% confidence interval (CI) of the selected actigraphic features for depression subsets in each cross-validation (CV) fold. SMD was computed using the mean difference divided by the pooled standard deviation over each fold subset. Aggregates are sorted by effect size and grouped by aggregation approach: mean (μ), standard deviation (σ), and correlation (ρ).

(M10—total activity during the 10 most active hours of the day, WASO—Wake After Sleep Onset, M10 RMSSD—Root Mean Square of Successive Differences within 10 most active hours each day, sleep RMSSD—Root Mean Square of Successive Differences of activity during the main daily sleep period, daily SD—Standard Deviation of activity within a calendar day, for more details, see Supplementary Table S1)